

SELF-STUDY. WHAT IS IT AND HOW TO DO IT? (Steps towards success)

Jo'rayeva Begoyim Usmonovna

Student of Shakhrisabz State Pedagogical Institute

Abstract: This article will debate about self-study and how to do it as well as how to use it in our daily life. I am going to share my real experience which I conducted some research 6 months ago. That research was undertaken in my coursemate. We used self-study tips, resources , plans for achieving the target. So I decided to write about all the important stages for attaining success in our majors .**Keywords:** success, self-study, online website, research,CEFR and IELTS.

In today's world, all the people are occupied with learning any skill such as foreign language, computer skills or other sport activities. As these things, they have a hectic lifestyle but sometimes there will not be any results and efficiency. Maybe it is because of choosing wrong tutor to study or being unaware of using effective strategies to maximize productivity. One of these kinds of needs are called **self-study** which is well-accepted in particular areas. Self-studying, is a way of independently learning something at any time or pace, includes setting goals and measuring the progress . Most importantly, the standarts for progress and success are self-imposed which is that noone tells you what to do or when to do . For example, cramming for an exam in school or university or learning how to cook a new recipe , all of them are in self-studying. Essentially, there are music and art for learning by your own.If you do self-study in learning English, this guide will surely help you:

- 1.Make a clear plan
- 2.Use reliable sources
- 3.Choose material based on your level .

Regular exercise is boring, the most important thing is to correctly evaluate your ability! If you want to learn English now, a support teacher can show you the right direction. Selfstudy will help you improve your English.

You know that in this world there are a lot of things to do self-study. Last months, we finished making self-study with my groupmate whose name is Munisa. And I knew her knowledge before she started preparing for CEFR exam as a self-study. Her level was A 2 and at that time, I checked her each skill such as speaking, listening, reading as well as writing. She had no any information in some of them. So that she started learning about 4 skills from the scratch by herself in favour of some online materials that I had used. I also studied one month by myself for achieving C1 and of course, I got that due to the essential materials and regular strategies . The most important thing that you rely on is **discipline**. If you have this thing, you can be completely achievable in your every desire.I had this thing and my friend too. She used the books which were given exam tips and particular example tasks. For example, multilevel CEFR books and Cambridge books that are very beneficial to increase the score and understand the main idea of every skill particularly, the strategies and tips are the common one which can be found easily in these books. The first thing that we must do while self-studying, **setting the realistic goals** , are your goals achievable or not , if you desire only unattainable goals, reaching them also will be impossible as you will not have any opportunity to carry out them such as you are a girl and your major is teaching or medicine but you can not opt for being a singer which requires a special talent. And the second one is about making a schedule. You know that every person has their own plans and daily lifestyle but most of us can not use our time efficiently. This is mainly because, we want to carry out our goals just we

aspire but we do not focus on how to achieve them. So that we need to **make a schedule** for being a well-organized person. We are supposed to make plan for a month or a week maybe a day. By means of schedule, we handle to do our tasks on time successfully.

☆ Here are the pictures of learners who is preparing for approaching exams through self-study.

Third one is **maintaining study habits and environment**. This means that never lose your motivation and strive to keep going at all costs. As a rule, some people feel demotivated and bored when they started self-study as they have no discipline and they lose their hopes too. As a result, they leave their wishes to easier one. No , it can not be if the learner finds the solutions for his or her motivation and thinks more about the bright future or career after carrying out that goal, it will be really awesome and immediately that person will be able to high-achiever. This was the important thing that my friend and I obeyed strictly. The fourth is **studying according to your style**. Right, all people have different styles and they do their lessons in accordance with their fascinating ideas like someone wants decorations in his or her copybook which gives plenty of motivation to read repeatedly. But some learners like using different shapes or colours or using electronic materials instead of ordinary printed books or magazines. It is also a style . Fifth is about **doing regular self-tests**. After finishing any new topic , you are supposed to test yourself as you may have not enough knowledge about that topic or use quize bots and self-tests that can really help you to know about your understanding. The last one is about **consistency**. Consistency is a key! Follow all the rules that I said you. And think more about your parents, your goals, your sweet future. At that time, you will never break your consistency code. That is the most significant thing in learning anything . It may be your hobby, your major, your language capacity and your special skill. After practice and practice, all people achieve their directed aims. If you fail, do not be upset , do not be

disencouraged, all people make mistakes and failures. It is okay but do not forget where are these mistakes coming from? That is the point. Try to correct your weak sides. Then you will see the sun that is shining for you ♥

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